

Relativistic Features In Nonrelativistic Quantum Mechanics Part II

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The relativistic energy-momentum relationship $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$) incorporates space-time through velocity v which is part of $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$. Nevertheless, one may write an inner product of two 4-vectors: (p,E) and (x,t) yielding $-Et+px$. If one wishes this to be constant for all p and E , one may consider an interval $x_1-x_2=1/p$. In such a case the time interval is $t_1-t_2 = 1/E$. (One may consider these values multiplied by a fixed number which may be fixed by nature.) Thus special relativity without any quantum mechanics defines a "special" length $1/p$ and a special time $1/E$. These are the wavelength and frequency used in quantum mechanics. This is not necessarily surprising as the classical Maxwell electromagnetic equations which are Lorentz invariant already lead to frequency and wavelength. This was known for quite some time and was not considered part of quantum mechanics although now it is.

One may ask why a special length $1/p$ (i.e. a wavelength) and time $1/E$ are not used in classical physics. We argue it is due to the numerical values of these quantities. $1/p$ is of the order of (10 to the power -10 m) or (10 to the power of -15 m) for small particles such as electrons or nucleons. Heavier classical masses would have even smaller lengths which cannot be perceived (although now there exist experiments which determine tiny movements (the size of an atom) in large macroscopic objects (e.g. 70 kg or more)).

In this note we examine these ideas in connection with quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity and Inner Products

The Einstein momentum-energy relationship includes the idea of space-time through the presence of velocity v i.e.

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{and} \quad E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad p = mv / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((1))$$

Nevertheless one may form an inner product between the two four vectors (p,E) and (x,t) i.e.

$$-Et + px \quad ((2))$$

$((2))$ often appears in wave expressions i.e. $\exp(-iEt + px)$ with the focus in the literature seeming to be the calculation of either a phase or group velocity. This is a little unusual because a velocity v already exists within E and p . In this note we thus ask: What is the relevance of $((2))$?

If one sets $((2))$ equal to a constant for all p and E , one may consider an x interval equal to $1/p$. This leads to a time interval equal to $1/E$. (These two values may be multiplied by an arbitrary number which is related to Planck's constant which was already applied to the photon. It would thus need to be reapplied in this case.) As a result there seems to exist a special physical length proportional to $1/p$ and a special period proportional to $1/E$ in classical special relativity with no quantum mechanical ideas present. This immediately begs the question: Why

do these not appear in classical physics? Classical physics deals with values at each $x(t)$, there is no interval or nonlocality.

We argue in this note that the length $1/p$ is very small. For a tiny object such as an electron or nucleon it is already of the order of $(10 \text{ to the power } -10 \text{ m})$ and $(10 \text{ to the power } -15 \text{ m})$ respectively. Even heavier objects would have small length intervals which seem to be completely “invisible” in classical scenarios.

Implications of a Special Length and Period in Special Relativity

As noted, the existence of a special length and period in special relativity is already at odds with the idea of classical physics that one may know values at each $x(t)$. The special length implies nonlocality which is a function of p , namely proportional to $1/p$. For very high p it is very small, but for lower p values it becomes larger. Thus special relativity introduces a resolution scale into the dimension of length. This is interesting because one may always place a z axis along the momentum direction thus seeing only one dimension, but p defines the resolution of length along this direction. Furthermore, for a fixed magnitude of p there are two directions (p and $-p$).

Given a special space interval $1/p$ associated with p , it seems there should be some ambiguity within such a region. Secondly, this interval repeats itself indefinitely suggesting periodicity. How does one consider p and $-p$ in such a scheme? In one case there is periodicity in one direction and in the other in the other direction. Thus one has two values $|p|$ and its sign together with a kind of periodicity. This suggests extending the one dimensional problem with two directions into a two dimensional periodic representation namely:

$$\exp(ipx) \text{ and } \exp(-ipx) \quad ((3))$$

The result ((3)) follows without any concept of quantum mechanics i.e. directly from the idea of a special length in special relativity.

Link with Quantum Mechanics

In Part I of this note we argued that in quantum mechanics one considers a potential $V(x)$ as consisting of different impulse hits. Thus for $V(x)$, which is tied to classical physics, knowledge of $x(t)$ (acceleration etc) is really a statistical average of various impulses each with their own probability. This probability is found through:

$$P(\text{particle with } p) \text{ } P(\text{impulse } k \text{ from potential}) \text{ proportional to } P(\text{particle with } p+k) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{A solution is } P(\text{particle with } p) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

This is the same result as ((3)), but obtained in a different manner. Nevertheless ((5)) implies a special length proportional to $1/p$ and includes periodicity. Again one has a nonlocal theory and there is ambiguity within the length $1/p$. This is consistent with a complex probability $\exp(ipx)$

which allows for interference (superposition) when adding these complex, periodic terms. It is, however, very different from both classical and classical statistical probability.

It is interesting to note that quantum mechanics uses the idea of probability whereas special relativity only introduces a wavelength and period. Quantum mechanics uses probability because impulse hits and their weights (or probabilities) must recreate $V(x)$ which is strictly classical and yields predictions at $x(t)$. Furthermore quantum mechanical averages for a bound state are linked to directly to classical mechanics i.e.

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } a(p) \text{ exp}(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \text{ exp}(ipx)] + V(x) = E \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is exactly of the form of a classical mechanical equation with the first term, average kinetic energy, corresponding to the classical $KE(x)$.

A probabilistic view arises when one tries to link probabilities related to a wavelength to classical results. Thus quantum mechanics seems to take the idea of a wavelength and period which seem to result in special relativity one step further and link them in a probabilistic/average manner to classical physics i.e. ((6)).

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the idea of wavelength and period exist in special relativity without any quantum mechanical arguments needed. We note that E and p in special relativity already contain space-time through velocity v and consider the relevance of the inner product of (p, E) and (x, t) i.e. $-Et + px$. We argue that for this to be constant for all p and E , one may choose a length interval x_1-x_2 proportional to $1/p$. This leads to a time interval t_1-t_2 proportional to $1/E$. Thus there is already a special length (wavelength) proportional to $1/p$ and a special period proportional to $1/E$ in special relativity. These are not considered in classical physics due to their extremely small values. Small masses (electrons, nucleons) yield sizes of (10 to the power -10 m) and (10 to the power -15 m) and larger classical masses even smaller sizes. If one could have systems, however, of this size (e.g. atoms and nuclei), then the interval of $1/p$ would be important. In such a case one would no longer have classical physics for which one knows all information at each $x(t)$. Given that one has special space intervals related to $1/p$, it seems there is a resolution of space. Furthermore one may have a particle move in the forward or backward direction. This suggests a kind of periodicity that can distinguish between these two motions. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are a possible solution. Thus we argue that the wavefunctions from quantum mechanics (free particle) may follow directly from special relativity.

In quantum mechanics one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ in a different manner, but at least one implication is the same as that of special relativity, namely the wavelength. In a quantum bound state one takes $V(x)$ which is linked with the classical view of $x(t)$ and assumes it is an average of impulse hits and their probabilities. Thus one has a probabilistic or statistical scenario from the outset. The idea of wavelength enters through the requirement:
 $P(\text{particle with momentum } p) P(\text{k impulse hit from potential})$ proportional to $P(\text{particle with momentum } p+k)$

This leads to a possible solution of $\exp(ipx)$ which introduces the idea of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ which exists in special relativity.